

MIMS 1.12

Self-consistency of the “Big G” Diagram

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September 2021

ABSTRACT

Philosophies, right or wrong, useful or worthless, should be internally self-consistent. The power of the Plasma-electromagnetic Cosmology¹ is its ability to make and test predictions, and match empirically proven science, rather than relying upon mathemagic. There are no pseudoscientific hypotheses in real PEMC work². In EPEMC³ we are able to *extend* past some limits, but not past the standards⁴, even in the Philosophy series, such as MIMS, or Strategy Series. However, what about the internal self-consistency of relying upon PEMC *and* Chinese Sciences and metaphysics? Does Chinese Natural Philosophae⁵ provide the sort of reliability that rationalism in western sciences would require?

In this short treatment, a description of the consistency is “proven” in the Big G diagram (as a followup to MIMS 1.11⁶), and then some other remarks with some tabular demonstration of the 2,3,5 harmonics within EPEMC overall.

Keywords: EPEMC - MIMS - God - Chinese Sciences - Polar Complete Wholeness

¹ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc>

² <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/volunteer>

³ https://www.academia.edu/36753648/Extended_Plasma_Electromagnetic_Cosmology_EPEMC

⁴ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/home/standards>

⁵ https://www.academia.edu/37784032/Chinese_Natural_Philosophy_Physics_in_EPEMC

⁶ https://www.academia.edu/53271235/Explication_of_the_Versatility_of_the_Big_G_diagram_in_MIMS_1_0

The Fibonacci Standard in MIMS

Among the powers, the most concrete (Earth) powers are the F , N , and P powers (See Figure 2,) while the more invisible are the L , A , and G powers, which are to some, matters of faith. However, they are not, but are matters of mathematical precision. Quoting from a previous MIMS paper⁷,

“This is a philosophical paper and that is a philosophical question not easily tackled by objective or materialistic-reductionistic sciences. Moreover, the only problem some scientists appear to have is with the concept of the Deity, but indeed it can be shown that there are at least 5 verifiable solutions to the existence vs. non-existence of God:

1. Yes, because of the filamented network of matter and energy, which is cyclical and self-contained, and continuously re-arranging
 - a. 1b: yes because the Big Bang was a moment of Creationism.
 - b. 1c: yes because the filamented structure shows self-organizing properties of neuronal structures indicating a kind of complexity-mediated structure akin to consciousness
2. Yes, because every culture around the world recorded a hermaphrodite fertility storm-god, identifiable as either an early but aged dwarf star, or Saturn, or later in middle-aged cultures Jupiter
 - a. 2b: yes because many middle to new aged cultures describe a Heracleian messiah, a son, who is a “new sun” based on a previous Heavenly Father and sent as a redeemer for #2
3. Yes, because there is a similarity of concept and data presence for the matrix [God] as [no-God] relying on the same (parameters); chiefly: omnipotence, infiniteness, immortality, omniscience, universal connection (usually love or sex)
4. Yes, because of the Dirac Delta mystical proof⁸ which is essential to describing current

1. Dirac delta function

In the lecture it was discussed that the Dirac delta function $\delta(x)$ as a extremely peaked Lorentz or a Gauß curve. As an alternative show that for $n \rightarrow \infty$ we can use the following sequences of functions as a representation of the Dirac delta function.

a)

$$\delta_n(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{n}{2} & |x| < \frac{1}{n} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

b) $\delta_n(x) = np(nx)$, where the function $p(x)$ satisfies $\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} p(x)dx = 1$

c) $\delta_n(x) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-n}^n e^{ixt} dt$

Hint: Given a test function $f(x)$ which is continuous at $x = 0$ and vanishes for $x \rightarrow \pm\infty$. Prove the filter property of the delta function: $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dx f(x) \delta_n(x) = f(0)$. Use suitable substitutions to simplify the integrals and look up the definite integral $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} t^{-1} \sin t dt$

Figure 1 - Dirac Delta Function

⁷ https://www.academia.edu/50804855/MIMS_2_Applications_discussions pp. 13

⁸ Mystical agency

5. Yes, because *electromagnetism relies upon the imaginary number and waves cannot be describe with it*
 a. *5b: yes because of irrational constants; both for irrationality and for constancy (tuning)*

This mathematical precision is reinforced in the Chinese metaphysics, which by the author is termed the “bagua dharma”, but enfolded into MIMS & EPEMC is now known as the 8 Laws or Principles of the P power:

		(Bagua)	(Wu Xing)	(Physics)
1. Causality	-	Heaven		
2. Flux/Evolution/Change	-	Wind	Wood	Gas
3. Relativity	-	River/Abys	Water	Liquid
4. Conservation	-	Mountain		
5. Vibration (Quantum)	-	Earth	Earth	Solid
6. Rotation	-	Thunder	Metal	Electromagnetism ⁹
7. Polarity	-	Fire	Fire	Plasma
8. Resonance/Harmony	-	Lake/Joy		

(1) The Chinese [complete] “Fibonacci” is 0 1 1 2 3 5 8 13

Therefore, can we see this consistency in the MIMS 1.10? Yes, we did in Tables 1 & 2. Also we say it in MIMS 2.62 in Table 1¹⁰, where all the strategy series received a dual support of MIMS and the power of the Fibonacci. However, is it present explicitly in the “Big G”?

Figure 2 - “Big G” diagram, augmented; credit: author

⁹ PEMF = Unified Aether Field, but in the 5 layer breakdown we stay consistent with the polar name.

¹⁰ https://www.academia.edu/51643169/MIMS_2_6_2_Strategy_and_Dualism pp. 4

The first 0 is the “hundun” or undifferentiated chaos referred to in the *Pangu Myth*, also known as Wuji. Technically speaking the EPEMC would say that the 0 represents the space where the counterspace percolates Aether into the space. The first 1 is the actual flow, or unity throughout, in a inward or outward spiral (as AGN like SGR A* push out through the galaxies), and is the prajna/ka/Qi or “true Tao” (DAO), which itself informs the Force. It is not that the Force is the Tao, but this is our closest cultural relative. Another name for these two “first Heaven and Earth” or “first Yang and Yin” is the Taiyi, or Great Unity. From there the fibonacci is continuous, with the final “13” being literally referenced in the New Testament (and thus why leyasu/Yeshua/Jesus chose 13 men to be his apostles). It is a euphemism for the “10,000 things” or everything, more commonly called in mystical circles “It All.”

At each level there are multiple 2, 3, 5 harmonics¹¹, among others:

Table 1 - Self-Consistency in EPEMC

Heaven	Water	Fire	Earth	Metal	Wood	Mountain	Lake
0	Hundun (CHAOS)	Wuji (Void)	Spongy Counter Space	Space	Causality	Mechanics & Kinetics	Newton et al.
1	Tao	Taote ¹²	Shang Di ¹³	Flux	Evolution	Gases	Spectroscopy
1	Taiji	Di /\	Heaven	The Lord	Relativity	Liquids	Hydro-dynamics
2	Yin (Egg)	Yang (Son)	Earth	Force	Polarity	Plasmas	HEP, fusion
3			Man (consciousness)	Aether	Conservation	Solids	Crystals & Thermo-dynamics ¹⁴
5				Numbers	Vibration	Electricity ¹⁵	EMF/EHD QED/QCD
8				Principles	Rotation	Gravity ¹⁶	SR/GR
13				[math]	Resonance	Magnetism	MHD

¹¹ The Chinese showed long ago that all WuXing/pentacle flows have several dual and tri “dosha” like harmonics.

¹² Where te 德 is the expression of the power of Tao 道, through the observer’s observation and containment. The “Great [Squatter] Man” was symbolic of God, because of the associative power and control of the 4 gas giants after their arising. See MIMS 1.10 p. 3

¹³ https://www.academia.edu/38590072/Shang_Di_Heaven_and_Dao

¹⁴ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Gvr_BcH1Cmw&list=PLnU8XK0C8oTAXk4bT4S7WT_SCgG3ZS-Uy

¹⁵ Unified Electro+weak+strong forces... the entirety of motion, spin, and orientations within the atom and subatomic structures, measured in eV (electronvolts)

¹⁶ Taken with the Law of Rotation to be the Kepler Laws of Motion. Thus Causality and Rotation (Heaven and Thunder, lit: God’s Weapon) are in close relationship as well. Therefore the God = the Weapon is a common motif.

Explications of Table 1

1. The number of columns is 8, the number of rows below the headers is 8, consistent with the *P* power, but **power** in general.
2. The Heaven Column has code control - this is true Heaven (not Kingdom), known as CH'IEN - the Creative, covered in MIMS 1.0 from the I Ching #1.¹⁷
3. Water and Fire are opposites (duals), and so provide the best polarity for the two columns as the fire column is a total transformation of the water column. Together, they are a polar complete pairing as the first broken line, while the Heaven column - the numbers - are completely yang.
 - a. The Void transforms chaos into the blackness
 - b. Taote makes Tao *real (manifest)*
 - c. God is the manifestation of Taiji (The Grand Ultimate) concept
 - i. The Taiji is the combination of Hundun and Tao
 - d. The suns are the father-son motif played out since the first egg “hatched”; this was Shamash, the brown dwarf star.
 - e. All of these are 1, and yet separated.
4. The Green Group represents Table 2 of the other paper, and all things which are in Aetheric form, and indistinguishable from fantasy, yet are concretely real.
 - a. Heaven forms a pairing of God’s “above power” and the infinite Source from whence it is derived.
5. Space and Flux (pink) act as 1 space-time, because space is nonexistent, and the flux is real, so time *appears to be*.
 - a. Time is merely the observation of the passage of events and change in matter or behavior.
6. The Blue Group represent the WuXing “meat and potatoes” of the “Big G” diagram
 - a. Heaven and Lord form the pairing known as “The Kingdom”, Olympia, etc.
7. The Force and other electricity related items are bolded.
8. The Purple group represents the four phases of matter
9. The teal group the 3 main forces governing everything
10. Rotation and Gravity make up a pairing for governing *motion* of matter
11. Math is the result of combining the P and N powers, it is a natural tool (like an axe or knife) expression of a more concrete form.
 - a. Attempts to make the abstract the reality, or even God will lead to natural failures, like SUSY

The author feels that this is internally self-consistent and self-evidently so.

Conclusion

The author is confident that the MIMS framework, and especially the “Big G” diagram will survive numerous means of attack from rationalists, logicians, numerologists, mathematicians, physicists, experiment, because it is rooted in ancient, sound philosophies, real numerological coding, and a working cosmology.

¹⁷

https://www.academia.edu/50300514/On_the_Membranous_Interface_of_the_Material_and_the_Spiritual_from_an_EPE_MC_perspective_and_Dual_Double_Layer_Economics_a_proposed_test_of_EPEMCs_metallic_properties_tensile_strength_malleability_durability

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